

ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF EXTENSION ACTIVITIES TO PANSOL NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The College of Teacher Education continuously provides assistance to its partner- beneficiaries through community-oriented extension service activities and outreach projects. Through these extension activities, the faculty and students of the College demonstrate their commitment in sharing their expertise in their respective fields to public and students and even indigent communities. The study was carried out to assess the impact of the extension activities conducted at Pansol National High School from 2018-2020. Specifically, the study described the extension activities of CTE-Graduate School as assessed by the respondents in terms of resource persons, topics provided, mechanics, faculty extensionists, and monitoring and feedbacking; ascertained the impact of extension activities conducted by CTE-Graduate School to the development of the respondents' management skills relative to decision making, organizing, human relations, communication, and supervisory; assessed the impact of extension activities to the research engagement of the respondents, determined the issues and challenges related to the conduct of extension activities, and proposed a plan of action for sustainable extension programs. The study used a descriptive type of research with a researcher-made questionnaire as the main data gathering instrument. It employed weighted mean and composite mean to analyze the data. The findings revealed that with respect to the description of extension activities, topics provided obtained the highest assessment by the respondents; the extension activities of the CTE-Graduate School for Master of Arts in Education major in Educational Management had a high impact on the development of management skills of the participants, the extension activities had a moderate impact on the research engagement of the participants. The study concluded that the issue and challenge that was always encountered by the respondents was diversifying extension activities, and the proposed plan of action for sustainable extension programs consists of specific objectives, activities, strategies, persons involved, sources of budget, and success indicators.

Keywords: educational management; impact of the extension services; descriptive study, weighted and composite means; Philippines